

FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF CORRUGATED CORE PANEL UNDER OUT-OF-PLANE LOADING

Kenan Çınar¹, Fatih E. Öz², Nuri Ersoy²

¹Mechanical Engineering Department, Namık Kemal University, Tekirdağ, Turkey,
Email: kcinar@nku.edu.tr, web page: <http://www.composites.boun.edu.tr>

²Mechanical Engineering Department, Bogazici University, Istanbul, Turkey,
Email: fatih.oz@boun.edu.tr, web page: <http://www.composites.boun.edu.tr>

³Mechanical Engineering Department, Bogazici University, Istanbul, Turkey,
Email: nuri.ersoy@boun.edu.tr, web page: <http://www.composites.boun.edu.tr>

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to investigate the failure behaviour of a panel with a novel corrugated core design under out-of-plane loading conditions. AS4/8552 prepreg system was used for both facesheet and core material and two different core designs are compared. Three-point bending tests were performed and acoustic emission monitoring technique was used to investigate the failure modes. It was observed that first matrix failure occurred at the corner sections of the panels and delamination initiated at these regions, followed by fibre failure at the ribs and facesheet. Acoustic emission signal clustering around certain frequencies was matched to various failure modes in order to provide an insight for further research on structural health monitoring by acoustic emission.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich panels are desirable for transportation industry such as aerospace, automotive, marine, as well as civil engineering applications due to their high stiffness/strength to weight ratio, and high corrosion resistance. The conventional sandwich panels are composed of polymeric and metallic honeycombs and foams [1-3]. Especially shear dependant mechanical properties of these sandwich panels are low, which encourages the researchers to design and manufacture new core structures [4-12].

Wang et al.[4] studied the performance of 2-D lattice trusses as a new core material inside the sandwich panel. Prepreg material with a designation of T700/TDE85 was used to manufacture the panels by hot press method. Prepregs were rolled into rods and placed inside the semi-circular grooves of the moulds. Then unidirectional prepregs were laid to be top and bottom surfaces of the same moulds with the previously defined stacking sequence. Both ends of the truss members were dispersed and gradually embedded into the prepregs of face sheets. They explored the behaviour of the panels under out-of-plane compression, shear and three-point bending. They concluded that delamination was the main weakness and occurred around the area where truss members were embedded into face sheets. Xu et al. [5] suggested a new idea related to lattice core based sandwich panels. Graded lattice core based sandwich panels were designed and manufactured. The core structure was gradually varied in the length direction of the panel. They found the failure strengths of the panels analytically as well as the optimum dimensions of the geometric parameters to minimize the weight under three-point bending. In the study of Wang et al. [6], trusses which form the lattice core were perpendicular to the facesheets. Fan et al.[7] designed and manufactured sandwich panels with Kagome lattice cores. It was shown that the carbon fibre reinforced lattice grids are much stiffer and stronger than foams and honeycombs. Buckling and debonding were observed and dominate the mechanical behaviour of the panels. To restrict debonding failure of the lattice core sandwich panels, much compliant skins were designed and tested [8]. T300 carbon fibres were used for the facesheets; however the thickness and the stacking sequence were changed. It was found that panels with more compliant face sheets resulted

in mono-cell buckling succeeding local buckling. In addition, it was advised that the fracture toughness of the adhering regions must be increased and the cell dimensions should be decreased to increase the debonding resistant. This Kagome lattice core was also used at cylindrical sandwich structures [9]. Mohamed et al. [11] used polyurethane foam as core material with different core designs such as closed cell box, trapezoid shape and web-core box, and sandwich panels using these core designs were manufactured using VARTM process. It was found that the trapezoid shape foam core had a flexural strength four times higher than the other counterparts. The main drawbacks of the above mentioned studies are the debonding between core and facesheets due to low contact and adhering surface within the truss and lattice core. In this study two particular fibre reinforced core designs are proposed with higher contact surface as compared to their counterparts. To the author's knowledge, prepreg is used for the first time in the literature to manufacture an integral corrugated core with stiffening ribs with a single processing step, instead of manufacturing corrugated core and facesheets separately and assembling the final plate structure by secondary bonding.

In addition to new sandwich plate design, acoustic emission (AE) system was used extensively to identify failure modes and monitor damage accumulation during the tests. It is mostly used for tensile testing of composite materials. In most of the studies, failure modes were classified according to peak frequency contents of AE signals [13-17]. In addition to peak frequency classification, some studies [15-18] classify failure modes with respect to some clustering algorithms but even in clustering methods, the most dominant AE parameter for classification was found to be peak frequency and the clusters were based on the peak frequency contents. Therefore, classification of failure modes with respect to peak frequency values is considered to be sufficient in this study. There are very limited studies available in literature about the application of AE system for testing corrugated stiffened plates. Nanayakkara et. al [19] used z-pins made of unidirectional carbon filament rods to improve the through-thickness compression strength of sandwich composite plates. The failure behaviour of these panels was investigated using acoustic emission system. It was found that, z-pins failed during loading but still compressive properties increased with volume fraction of z-pins. This was shown by comparing AE recording of z-pinned and non-stiffened plates. Although, damage initiated in z-pins at early stages of loading, they were still able to carry load. Pashmforoush et. al. [20] used AE registration technique for identification of failure modes during mode I delamination testing of GFRP sandwich panels with polyethylene foam core. They used k-means algorithm for clustering. As it was found in previous studies that peak frequency parameter is the best identifier to characterize the failure mode. Ben Ammar et. al. [21] investigated the effect of foam density on the mechanical behaviour of PVC cored GFRP sandwich plate with AE system to identify local damage under 4-point bending test. It was found that each cluster is found to correspond to a different damage mode.

In this study, the failure mechanism of carbon fibre reinforced polymeric corrugated plate is investigated under three-point bending tests. Two different core structures and lay-up sequences were tested and compared to each other. AE registration method was used to identify the failure modes. MISTRAS AE system is used during the tests. The sensors used are PK15I sensors with an operating frequency range of 100-450 kHz. The resonance frequency and a pre-amplification level of the sensors are 150 kHz and 20 dB, respectively.

2 MANUFACTURING METHOD

AS4/8552 prepreg material system was used for both the core and the facesheets. Aluminium mandrels were used to form the prepreg core structure of the panel. The thickness and width of the aluminium mandrels were 25 mm and 50 mm, respectively. For the core material, two different lay-up methods were used. The schematic representation of the first lay-up method is seen in Figure 1(a). Firstly, 4 plies of prepreg material which will form the bottom facesheet were laid up on a steel tool. Then another four-layer of prepreg is pre-stacked to form the core, which is the second step represented in Figure 1(a). Core layer is laid on the bottom facesheet by sequentially placing the aluminium mandrels and then bending the core sheet to take a zig-zag shape around the aluminium mandrels, which is the third step represented in Figure 1(a). After placing all aluminium mandrels and the prepreg core material, another stack of prepreg material with stacking $[0/90]_{2s}$ was laid-up on these assembled aluminium mandrels and prepreg core to form the upper facesheet. A steel caul plate was

placed for obtaining uniform thickness on the upper facesheet. Finally all parts were covered by conventional vacuum bagging materials and they were cured in an autoclave. Manufacturer Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC) [22] was used for curing of the panels in the autoclave. After curing, all aluminium mandrels were removed easily from the panels at the room temperature, thanks to the mould release film wrapped around the aluminium mandrels and the differential coefficients of expansion of the aluminium and composite.

The schematic representation of the second lay-up method is seen in Figure 1(b). For this lay-up method, firstly 7 plies of prepreg material with stacking sequence of $[0/90/90/0/0/90/90]$ were laid up on a steel tool for lower facesheet. Secondly, a single layer of prepreg is wrapped around aluminium mandrels one by one in such a way that fibre direction is along the periphery of the cross-section of the mandrel. Then other plies of 90° and 0° were laid up on both sides of the aluminium mandrel to provide symmetry. The stacking sequence of ribs is $[0/0/90]_s$. These aluminium blocks wrapped with prepregs were then placed on the previously laid up lower facesheet. Then another facesheet of same stacking sequence was placed on these aluminium mandrels to form the upper facesheet. A steel caul plate was placed on the upper facesheet. Finally all parts were covered by classical vacuum bagging materials and they were cured in the autoclave according to the MRCC. One of the manufactured panels can be seen in Figure 1(c).

Five sandwich panels in total with the dimensions of 280x453 mm were manufactured using these lay-up methods. The sandwich panels have 9 closed cells which run in the longitudinal direction. Three of panels were manufactured using the first lay-up method. The stacking sequence used for upper and the lower face sheets were $[0/90]_{2s}$. For the core sheets, $[0/90]_s$ stacking sequence was used. Also, two panels were manufactured using the second lay-up method. For the second lay-up method, the stacking sequence of the facesheets and the ribs were $[0/90/90/0]_s$, and $[0/0/90]_s$ respectively. The thickness of the facesheets and the core ribs are 1.40 and 1.10 mm respectively. Three point bending test specimens in the longitudinal and transverse directions are cut from the plate by a water cooled diamond disk.

Figure 1. (a) schematic representation of the first lay-up method. (b) schematic representation of the second lay-up method. (c) sample of sandwich panel.

3 FAILURE BEHAVIOUR OF SANDWICH PANELS

3.1 Three-Point Bending Tests-Transverse Direction

Three-point bending tests were carried out in accordance with ASTM C-393. The support span length was equal to 150 mm and the test speed was set to 6 mm/min. Dimensions and stacking

sequence of the specimens under the three-point bending test are given in Table 1.

Lay-up Method	Test Direction	Number of Samples	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Facesheet Stacking	Rib Stacking
1 st	Longitudinal	4	200	52.8	29.3	[0/90] _{2s}	[0/90] _s
	Transverse	3	260	73.6	29.3	[0/90] _{2s}	[0/90] _s
2 nd	Longitudinal	4	200	52.8	28.4	[0/90 ₂ /0] _s	[0 ₂ /90] _s
	Transverse	5	260	75.0	28.4	[0/90 ₂ /0] _s	[0 ₂ /90] _s

Table 1. Dimensions of specimens tested in three-point bending.

The load-displacement curves of samples manufactured according to the first lay-up method are shown in Figure 2(a) and snapshots showing progressive failure of the samples are presented in Figure 3. A linear region representing elastic deformation is followed by a drop in load due to matrix cracking at the corner section of the panels where larger matrix dominated regions occurred during manufacturing. The damage initiation occurred at load level 0.365 kN at a displacement of was displaced 4.3 mm. Final failure was delamination of facesheet as well as rib buckling and delamination, as represented in Figure 3(c). However, it is difficult to identify the failure modes within the complex geometries because different failure modes can occur at the different places at the same time. 5 failure modes were activated and they are classified with respect to their FFT frequency ranges, 25- 100 kHz, 120 – 170 kHz, 170 – 220 kHz, 220 – 280 kHz, and 340 – 400 kHz, which are represented by colour bands in Table 2 and the relevant figures. Table 2 shows the frequency ranges corresponding to various failure modes that are cited in the relevant literature [13-15], as well as the frequency ranges identified in this study by coupon tests performed. In these coupon tests, a carbon fibre bundle was embedded into the resin moulded in a dog bone shaped cavity and then cured. It was found that matrix cracking and matrix-fibre debonding occurs around 150 kHz and 250 kHz, respectively.

	Fibre	Resin	Sensor Range	Matrix crack	Delamination	Debondig	Fibre Failure	Fibre Pull-out
[13]	IM6	6376 epoxy	WD (62.5-562.5) kHz	90 < F < 180	240 < F < 310		300 < F	180 < F < 240
[14]	Glass	Polypropylene	WD (10-1000) kHz		F ≈ 100		F ≈ 450, F ≈ 550	200 < F < 300
[15]	IM7	8552 epoxy	WD (10-1000) kHz	0 < F < 50	50 < F < 150	200 < F < 300	400 < F < 500	500 < F < 600
Current study	AS4	8552 epoxy	PK151 (100-450) kHz	120<F<170	170<F<220	220<F<280	340<F<400	?

Table 2. Frequency ranges defined in literature and found in the current study.

By observing the colour bands in Figure 2(b), it can be said that most of the failure modes occur consecutively and were triggered at a displacement of 4.3 mm. The density of peak frequency values around 250 kHz, especially the number of values between 220 and 280 kHz, is increased after load dropped from 1.3 kN and the deflection reached to 16.5 mm as seen in Figure 2(b). According to the uniaxial tension test, it can be said that the peak frequency values around 250 kHz represent debonding failure modes. Also, highest peak frequency values between 350-400 kHz are frequent and they are believed to belong to fibre failure. The dense peak frequency around 200 kHz might be delamination failure mode because delamination can be seen in Figure 3(c). One interesting features of Figure 2(b) is reduction of the density of AE clusters after load drops in load-displacement curves.

Figure 2. (a) load-displacement curves and (b) acoustic emission peak frequency from three-point bending test of transverse samples manufactured using first lay-up method.

Figure 3. Three-point bending tests history of Set-2 panels tested along transverse direction.

Higher load carrying capacity was obtained with the second lay-up method, as seen in Figure 4. Figure 5 shows snapshots of progressive failure of one of the samples. Frequency ranges are similar to those of the samples manufactured according to the first lay-up method. However a new frequency range appears around 450 kHz. First failure occurred around 1.07 kN.

Matrix cracking was observed at the corner section of the panels like the previous set of panels as seen in Figure 5(a). However, when Figure 4 (b) is checked, it is seen that, occurrence density of AE signals around 250 kHz is higher than other frequency values. So, there is debonding occurring at the inner portions of the plate. This pattern continues until the displacement reaches to 15 mm where the load is 1.4 kN. At the same time, from this load level onwards, the density of AE signals with peak frequency value around 350 kHz is increased. They are believed to be fibre failure. Generally, fibre failure occurs at the corner sections through the width of the panel. The sudden drop at this load level is due to excessive matrix cracking. This can be seen at Figure 5 (a), where the occurrence density of peak frequency levels around 150 kHz is increased when the load dropped suddenly from 1.4 kN. Final failure was delamination of facesheet, which initiated from the corner section of the panels, as seen in Figure 5(c). Also, it can be seen from Figure 4 (b) that, the density of AE signals around 150 kHz is increasing through the end of the test. With the new design, the number of plies of the core walls increased from 4 plies to 6 plies, and this configuration prevented premature buckling of the ribs at early stages of loading. Thus, the strength of the plate increased as shown in Figure 4 (a).

Figure 4. (a) load-displacement curves and (b) acoustic emission peak frequency from three-point bending test of transverse samples manufactured according to the second lay-up method.

Figure 5. Three-point bending tests history of panels manufactured according to the second lay-up method tested along transverse direction.

3.2 Three-Point Bending Tests – Longitudinal Direction

Three-point bending tests were also carried out for panels along longitudinal direction, as represented in Figure 1(c). Load carrying capacity along this direction was higher for both panels manufactured by the first and the second lay-up method. Load- displacement curves for four samples are seen in Figure 6 (a) for panel manufactured by using the first lay-up method. Local buckling and delamination were observed at the upper loading leg of the three-point bending fixture. As it is seen in Figure 6 (b), similar peak frequency bands occurred at the test along longitudinal direction. There are hits recorded from the very early stages of the test which gave peak frequency values at 185 and 190 kHz and continued until the end of the test. This is believed to belong to delamination, as represented in Figure 7 (a). Their occurrence density increased when the deflection reached to 3.5 mm. Further increasing the deflection of the panel to 5.2 mm, new hits were recorded for matrix cracking and debonding with 146-151-156 kHz and 225-234 kHz peak frequencies respectively. With the load drop from 2.9 kN, each frequency range extended to lower and upper frequency values. In addition to this, signals representing fibre failure became visible and with a larger range than bending test in transverse direction, which is between 340 – 410 kHz. Interestingly, a very low peak frequency values were recorded from this load drop that is between 20 – 60 kHz. The reason of these signals is not known yet.

The panels manufactured with the second lay-up method gave higher load values as seen in Figure 8 (a). The reason is the stacking sequence of the ribs, which have more zero degree fibres along thickness direction of the sandwich panel. As shown in Figure 8 (b) almost no hits were recorded during loading until first failure which occurred at 3.9 kN. After this 6 failure modes were activated similar to previous tests. Delamination between the top facesheet and upper edge of the rib is the reason of the first load drop at 3.9 kN. The amount of delamination increases through the end of the test. This can be understood by the increase at the occurrence density of the AE hits around 200 kHz. Frequency density for debonding is increasing after load drop from 6.47 kN, which is around 250 kHz kHz. Also, fibre failure occurs from the first load drop until the end of the test which is represented by

frequencies around 350 kHz. In addition, the peak frequency ranges for fibre breakage is different between two sets. The peak frequency ranges for fibre breakage are between 350-400 kHz for the first set and the peak frequency ranges for fibre breakage are between 320-375 kHz for the second set.

Figure 6. (a) Load-displacement, (b) acoustic emission peak frequency curves for three-point bending test of panels along longitudinal direction-Set 2

Figure 7. Three-point bending tests history of Set-2 panels tested along longitudinal direction.

Figure 8. (a) Load-displacement (b) acoustic emission peak frequency curves for three-point bending test of panels manufactured according to the second lay-up method along longitudinal direction.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two particular lay-up methods were used to manufacture sandwich panels. Prepreg is used for the first time in the literature to manufacture an integral corrugated core with stiffening ribs in one processing step, instead of manufacturing corrugated core and facesheets separately and assembling the final plate structure by secondary bonding. Higher contact surface between the core and the facesheets is the main advantage of this manufacturing method as compared to counterpart examples. The failure behaviour of these panels under three-point bending tests was investigated by acoustic emission monitoring.

Acoustic emission monitoring is proved to be a useful guide to find failure modes within the more complex sandwich panels. 4 failure modes were activated and they are classified with respect to their FFT frequency ranges, 120 – 170 kHz, 170 – 220 kHz, 220 – 280 kHz, and 340 – 400 kHz, which are matrix cracking, delamination, debonding, and fibre failure, respectively. Along transverse direction, matrix cracking mainly occurred at the corner sections of the panels and followed by delamination from these matrix cracking regions. Along longitudinal direction, it was observed that delamination is the first failure. If load carrying capacity is compared, it was shown that the load carrying capacity of the panels along longitudinal direction were higher as compared to transverse direction. Also, panels manufactured using second lay-up method had more load carrying capacity due to their stacking sequence. In the future work, the angle of ribs might be optimized to increase the core shear strength.

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